

A Corpus-Based Study of Conjunctive Cohesion in Pakistani English Newspapers

Shafqet Yasmin¹, Humaira Irfan Khan², Afia Mahmood³

Abstract

This corpus-based study in the perspective of Pakistani English analyzed the use of conjunctive cohesive linkages as defined and categorized by Halliday and Hasan (1976) in the columns/articles published in the opinion section of Pakistani English Newspapers in the month of November 2022. A corpus of 141 columns of DAWN and The Express Tribune was developed and analyzed using the corpus software AntConc (4.1.4). The study revealed higher frequencies of conjunctive adjuncts of extension and enhancement types. Conjunctions of additive, causal and adversative sub-categories are found to be most favoured by the columnists of both Pakistani English newspapers. The tendency of usage is same among the most frequently used conjunctions; however, there are some differences in the choice of least used conjunctions between the writers of DAWN and The Express Tribune.

Keywords: Conjunction, Grammatical cohesion, Pakistani English, Corpus analysis

1. Introduction

1.1. Background to the Study

The wide spread use of English has earned it global status. English shares multiple statuses that range from a second or foreign language to the status of lingua franca and international language. English language around the globe is not the one used by its natives in UK. Englishes of different regions are different varieties of English with their own distinctive features embedded in the standard variety (Schneider 2003). English now is a language with less native and an ever-expanding number of non-native speakers (Crystal, 2003).

Pakistani English (Penglish) with its distinct features is a component of linguistic sub-family of South-Asian English (Baumgardner, 1993; Kachru, 1982; Rahman, 1991). English in South-Asia became 'nativized' and 'vernacularized' (Kachru, 1992; Mahboob and Ahmar, 2004; Rahman, 2020; Khan, 2012). Mahmood (2009) quotes Baumgardner (1988, 1993), Rahman (1991) and Talaat (2002) who refers Pakistani English as an independent variety with its own established norms. English shares a position in the outer circle of the three concentric circles' model shared by Kachru (2006).

According to Kirkpatrick (2007), phonology and pronunciation, vocabulary, morphology and grammar, and cultural conventions and schema are the main heads under which a linguistic variety is studied. Newspapers are an authentic source of vocabulary, grammar and writing conventions implied by the writers of the variety, Pakistani English in this case.

Martínez (2015) refers Halliday and Hasan (1976) framework that describes cohesion under a range of grammatical and lexical possibilities. Conjunction, discussed by Halliday and Hasan (1976) under the umbrella of grammatical cohesion, is a connective word/phrase that bridges the preceding clause with the following clause which helps the readers to make sense of the given text. Halliday and Hasan (1976) refer it as a systematic connection between the preceding and proceeding words and phrases.

A text, according to Halliday and Hasan (1976), has certain linguistic features that adds to its unity and give it a texture. Texture is a manifestation of cohesion. Haratyan (2011) presents cohesion as "non-structural text-forming relations" (Halliday and Hasan, 1976) developed through cohesive devices of reference, substitution, ellipsis, **conjunction** and lexical cohesion. Cohesion is generally rendered as inter-clausal conjunctive linkages that the writers develop in the text to give it unity and texture. (Qasim, Batool and Nawaz, 2020) quotes Halliday and Hasan (1976) who refer that conjunctive adjuncts are not cohesive in their own nature but have potential to link phases and bring in connectivity in the text by expressing definite meaning which lend help to presume the very occurrence of many other component elements in the written discourse.

According to Halliday, conjunctive adjuncts, that can be certain adverbial groups or prepositional phrases, establishes cohesive conjunctive linkages among clauses which are manifested in the text in terms of **elaboration**, **extension** and **enhancement**. (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014; Literary Stylistics Lecture Notes No. 18c, Ismail Talib: Conjunctive Cohesion, n.d.).

Around the world, a number of researchers have explored use of cohesion through cohesive devices in a variety of texts/written discourse and dimension of use. As far as use of cohesive items and writing quality are concerned, some studies (Castro, 2004; Zhang, 2010) reveal no significant relationship while others (Liu & Braine, 2005; Yang & Sun, 2012; Zhang, 2010) found this relationship significant. These studies were based on expository compositions or argumentative essays of Chinese and Filipino undergraduate learners.

Studies have also been conducted to identify problems in appropriate use of conjunctive cohesive linkages in the writings of ESL/EFL learners. In a corpus-based study on Japanese EFL learners, Narita, et. al. (2004) found an overuse of conjunctions 'first', 'in addition', 'moreover' and 'of course' while an under use of logical connectors like 'then', 'yet' and 'instead'. Chen (2006) in a study based on two corpora concluded that EFL learners frequently use conjunctions of

¹ PhD Scholar, DASS, University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan

² Associate Professor of English, DASS, University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan

³ PhD Scholar, DASS, University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan

additive category whereas professional writers are more frequent in using conjunctive adjuncts of adversative category. Another notable finding was of inappropriate and illogical use of conjunctions of therefore, e.g., therefore and besides. Hamed (2014) reported inappropriate use of cohesive conjunctions in his research on argumentative essays of Libyan EFL learners; there was a deficit in the use of adversative, additive and causal conjunctions. Ganie, Sinar and Yusuf (2021) explored use of cohesive conjunctive devices in the theses of Indonesian university students by employing both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies. The study concludes with a predominant use of conjunctions of additive category followed by cohesive markers of causal, adversative and temporal categories as per taxonomy of conjunctions laid by Halliday and Hasan. AlAttar and Abu-Ayyash (2022) found, in their study conducted on argumentative essays of Emirati students, no significant correlation in the use of conjunctions and production of quality texts. Further, they identified problems in using conjunctive adjuncts of adversative category as well as an overuse of ‘and’ by the students.

Source: The System of Conjunction; Halliday & Matthiessen (2013)

In many researches, conjunctive cohesion is investigated in written discourse to evaluate the varieties of purposes served by conjunctions in a variety of texts. A study based on a word count of 850 million obtained from three corpora (BNC, COCA and COHA) was conducted by Hutton and Curzan (2019) to investigate the perceptions regarding linguistic change with reference to the status of conjunction and found out modification in the usage of conjunction. Alasmri and Kruger (2018) compared the frequencies and functions of conjunctive markers in their study on Arabic texts. The comparison was drawn among parallel corpora of translated and non-translated texts of legal and creative genre. WordSmith Tools 7 was employed on the corpus of one thousand words; analysis revealed difference in the use of conjunctions across different types of texts. Chen (2017) compared the use of conjunctions in native English writings and written assignments of Chinese English learners. The comparison concluded more frequent use of conjunctions by native writers than Chinese EFL. This investigation also have its extension in the domain of research articles. Namaziandost, Nasri, and Keshmirshekan (2019) conducted a comparative study to analyse conjunctive cohesive devices employed in the research articles by Iranian and non-Iranian researchers in the field of applied linguistics. Purposive random sampling technique was used to select the articles published during 2015-2019 in Scopus-indexed journals. The findings reveal that articles

written by non-Iranian authors were of better quality with regards to use of cohesive conjunctive devices. The researchers like Jamalzadeh (2017) carried out a corpus based analysis on the use of cohesive conjunctions in the research articles of medical field. The researcher compared conjunctions used in the research articles written by Iranian and non-Iranian researchers. The analysis of four sections of research articles exhibited variation in the use of conjunctive adjuncts in the articles of the medical field. Conjunctive features were studied by many researchers around the world (Trebit; Ketabi and Jamalvand, 2009; Michel, 2013; Mohammad, 2015; Bahaziq, 2016). Jambak and Gurning (2014) found conjunctions (59.65%) as the most dominant cohesive devices in the headlines of The Jakarta Post with a predominant use of the conjunctive adjuncts of additive, adversative, causal and temporal categories.

In Pakistani context, Khan and Choudhary (2017) conducted a corpus-driven investigation on the use of conjunctions in the novels of Mohsin Hamid. Ahmad, Mahmood, Mahmood, and Siddique (2019) conducted a corpus assisted study to analyze most frequently used cohesive conjunctive markers, important to develop structural connection and communicative flow in the text, in abstracts of Pakistani research articles. Qasim, et al. (2020) conducted corpus-based analysis of 250 research articles across five academic disciplines of social sciences. They concluded high frequencies of conjunctive cohesive devices in the academic writings of the English learners. Learners show a higher tendency in use of conjunctions of additive, exemplification and causative sub-categories. Qasim, et al. (2021) explored employment of conjunctive markers in 400 essays (academic writing), extracted from ICNALE, through a corpus driven approach. For analysis, frequency of each conjunctive marker was compared with n-gram obtained from AntConc software. Ahmad, et al. (2019) analyzed the use of modal verbs in Pakistani English newspapers editorials. Shahnaz and Imtiaz (2014) conducted a discourse analysis of Zubeda Mustafa's article 'The Pleasure of Reading' published in Dawn and found that the newspaper writers do employ cohesive conjunctions to bring order and connectivity in the text; however, no research based analysis has been conducted to delineate the use of conjunctive cohesive devices in opinion sections of Pakistani English newspapers.

This paper will analyse the use of various types of conjunctive cohesion, based on conjunctive cohesion categories shared by Halliday and Hasan (1976), in Pakistani print media (English Newspapers). Articles published in the opinion section of the two main stream/ widely published daily English Newspapers. A corpus of the articles of all the writers published in month of November 2022 by the daily DAWN and The Express Tribune were selected for the present study to investigate the type and the frequency of use of conjunctive devices.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

The present research is developed around the below mentioned objectives:

- To measure the frequencies of various categories of cohesive conjunctive features.
- To compare the use of conjunctive cohesive features by column writers of opinion section across the two mainstream English newspapers of the country.

1.3. Research Questions

The investigation is based on the following research questions:

- What are the frequencies of various categories of conjunctive cohesive adjuncts in Pakistani English newspapers?
- To what extent are there meaningful similarities and differences in use of conjunctive cohesion by columnists of opinion section across the two Pakistani English newspapers?

1.4. Significance of the Study

The present study shares insights on Pakistani writers' choices of conjunctive adjuncts for developing function appropriate cohesive ties in newspaper texts. This in turn helps to envision the practices/distinctive features of Pakistani English in authentic texts that can be helpful for researchers and linguists in norms developing processes of Pakistani English.

2. Methodology

2.1. Overall Methodological Approach

The research study is descriptive in its approach. The quantitative data was collected and analyzed to calculate the frequency of use of various kinds of conjunctions as shared by Halliday and Hasan in their model.

2.2. Development of the Corpus

This study was based on the corpus of 141 article/columns published in the opinion sections of the two mainstream English Newspapers, DAWN and The Express Tribune, during the month of November 2022.

Table 1

<i>Size of the corpus</i>				
Newspaper	Articles	Total words	Percentage	
DAWN		43	41210	33.947%
The Express Tribune		98	80184	66.052 %
		141	121394	99.999=100%

2.3. Criteria for Developing Corpus

All the articles published during the month of November 2022 in the two mentioned Pakistani newspapers were selected for the development of the corpus. The articles were accessed through web based archives of the newspapers. Authors of

the articles in both newspapers were of varied capabilities with respect to their experience and field. The writers were young as well seasoned, having regularly weekly publications or once a month or even once a quarter. Hence, all the articles published in the month of November were consider for the development of the corpus.

Halliday's Model for Conjunctive Cohesion

Sub-types			Items	
ELABORATION:				
Apposition	expository		that is to say, in other words, I mean to say, put it another way	
	exemplifying		for instance, for example, thus, to illustrate	
Clarification	corrective		rather, or rather, at least, to be (more) precise, precisely	
	distractive		by the way, incidentally	
	dismissive		in any case, anyway, leaving that aside	
	particularizing		in particular, more especially, particularly	
	resumptive		as I was saying, to resume, to get back to the point, resuming	
	summative		briefly, to sum up, in conclusion	
	verifactive		actually, in fact, as a matter of fact	
Sub-types			Items	
EXTENSION				
Addition	positive	and	and, also, moreover, in addition, besides	
	negative	nor	Nor, neither	
	adversative	but	but, on the other hand, yet, however, conversely	
Variation	replacive		instead, on the contrary	
	subtractive		apart from that, except for that	
	alternative		alternatively	
Sub-types			Items	
ENHANCEMENT				
Spatio-Temporal	simple	following	then, next, afterwards	
		simultaneous	just then, at the same time, instantly	
		preceding	before that, before, hitherto, previously	
		conclusive	in the end, finally	
	complex	immediate	at once, thereupon, straightaway	
		interrupted	soon, after a while	
		repetitive	next time, on another occasion	
		specific	next day, an hour later, next morning	
		durative	meanwhile, all that time	
		terminal	until then, up to that point	
		punctiliar	at this moment	
simple internal	following	next, secondly, my next point is		
	simultaneous	at this point, here, now		
	preceding	hitherto, up to now		
	conclusive	lastly, last of all, finally		
Manner	comparison	positive	likewise, similarly, in the same way;	
		negative	in a different way	
	means		Thus, thereby, by such means, in the same manner	
Causal-conditional	general		so, then, therefore, consequently, hence, because of that, for	
	specific	result		in consequence, as a result
		reason		on account of this, for that/this reason
		purpose		for that purpose, with this/that/it in mind/view
		conditional positive		then, in this/that case, in this/that event, under the circumstances
		conditional negative		otherwise, if not
concessive		yet, still, though, despite this/that, even so, all the same, nevertheless, nonetheless, however		
Respective	positive		here, there, as to that, in this/that respect; as far as that's/it's concerned	
	negative		in other respects, elsewhere	

Source: Adapted from Halliday, M., & Matthiessen, C. (2013). Halliday's introduction to functional grammar

2.4. Data Retrieval

The below mentioned mechanism was formulated for quick retrieval of the data as and when required.

- Separate word files were maintained for both newspapers' articles. Articles of each writer were saved in the chronological order.
- A Microsoft Excel spreadsheet was maintained for quick retrieval of data like author name, article title, date of publication, data source, and word and token type.
- Word files were converted to text files with UTF-8 encoding.

3. Instruments for Data Analysis

Halliday's model of conjunctive cohesion was used that classifies the conjunctive adjuncts in to three main categories of elaboration, extension, and enhancement. Corpus analysis software AntConc (4.1.4) was used to analyse the developed corpus of Pakistani English newspaper articles.

3.1. Data Analysis

First of all, type to token ratio of DAWN and The Express Tribune articles was calculated through the text processor software AntConc (4.1.4). Then the conjunctive devices were categorized as per the types and sub-types suggested by Halliday's model of Conjunctive Cohesion. Further, the frequencies of the cohesive conjunctive adjuncts were counted, separately, for the data of both newspapers. A comparison of frequency of use of conjunctions by the writers of both Pakistani English newspapers was drawn.

4. Results

Results of the study reveal that the most frequently used are the additive conjunctions whereas the least used are the comparative conjunctive adjuncts. This trend with a slight variation is similar in both newspapers.

Table 2

<i>Frequencies of cohesive conjunctions</i>					
Types	Sub-Types	DAWN	Tribune	Total	Type Total
Elaboration	Apposition	37	70	107	300
	Clarification	71	122	193	
	Addition	1271	3111	4382	
Extension	Adversative	324	373	697	5117
	Variation	15	23	38	
	Spatio-Temporal	130	240	370	
Enhancement	Comparative	3	13	16	2588
	Causal-conditional	677	1191	1868	
	Respective	142	192	334	

Among the three functional classes or types of conjunctions, conjunctive adjuncts of extension category got the highest frequency of use by the column writers of both Pakistani English Newspapers. The cohesive devices of 'enhancement' category follows the category of extension. The least usage is of the conjunctive adjuncts of the elaboration category. This trend highlights the focused textual purposes/functions with respect to opinion writing in the English newspapers.

Figure 1: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts in three major categories

In every conjunctive class one sub-type gets the dominant frequency like in elaboration, the conjunctive adjuncts of clarification are more frequently used by the writers of both newspapers than the adjuncts of apposition. Similarly, in the category of extension, additive purposes are the most dominant one. In the same vein, causal-conditional purposes are the paramount among others purposes of Spatio-Temporal, comparative and respective nature.

4.1. Elaboration

In the system of conjunctions (Halliday and Hasan, 1976), Elaboration is the first type, based on the function served by the conjunctions, which is further divided in subtypes of Apposition and Clarification.

4.2. Apposition

Among conjunctions of Appositive category, ‘that is’ from the sub-category of ‘expository’ is more frequently used in both newspapers with a frequency of 47 in total; however, usage is slightly more frequent in the Tribune data. Whereas the cohesive device ‘I mean’ is not used at all by the writers. Further, for the purpose of exemplification, ‘thus’ with a total frequency of 37 is the most frequently opted conjunction whereas ‘to illustrate’ is not at all used by the Pakistani column writers. The most common conjunctive phrase ‘for instance’ and ‘for example’ are also not that favourite of the writers of both newspapers in comparison to other conjunctions of this category. While keeping in consideration the type token ratio of the two newspapers’ corpora, the study shows that the columnists of the The Express Tribune show an increased tendency for the use of ‘for instance’ and ‘for example’.

Figure 2: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts in the category of apposition

4.3. Clarification

Data reveals that the conjunctions of ‘corrective’, ‘particularizing’ and ‘varificative’ sub-categories are more frequently chosen by the writes to meet the purposes of clarification in the text. Conjunctions most frequently opted by the writers are ‘rather’ (57), ‘particularly’ (32) and ‘especially’ (30). ‘At least’ (13), ‘in particular’ (12), ‘actually’ (18), and ‘in fact’ (18) are the less frequently used conjunctions for the purpose of clarification in the text. ‘Precisely’ (4) though used for a very few times is favoured by the DAWN writers in comparison to Tribune writers despite having comparatively bigger corpus.

Figure 3: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts in the category of clarification

The study reveals that in this category certain conjunctive adjuncts like ‘or rather’ (0), ‘to be precise or more precise’(0), ‘in particular’(12), and more especially’(0) given in Halliday and Hasan’s model are either not used or least used; however, their alternates like ‘rather’(57), ‘particularly’(32) and ‘especially’(30) are not only used but also used frequently for the clarification purposes.

The conjunction of ‘rather’ of corrective category is most frequently used among all other conjunctions of this category. Further, the writers of The Express Tribune newspaper have used it at more instances than columnists of DAWN. ‘At least’, ‘anyway’ and ‘in fact’ shows almost similar numbers for use by both newspapers but considering the word count of both corpora it can be said that DAWN writers have a greater tendency towards using the above cited three conjunctions.

The conjunctions of ‘incidentally’ (01), ‘briefly’ (01) and ‘as a matter of fact’ (03) though with a very low frequency of usage are used by The Tribune writers only. The use of conjunctions of ‘distractive’ (01), ‘dismissive’ (04), ‘summative’ (01) categories is almost negligible whereas no conjunction of ‘resumptive’ category is at all used by the writers of both Pakistan newspapers. Thus, the study presents that for elaboration purposes, the corrective (rather; 57) category is most frequently used followed by conjunctions of exposition (that is; 47) and exemplification (thus; 37) in both Pakistani newspapers.

4.4. Extension

The second main textual function served by the Conjunctive cohesion is extension. The conjunctive adjuncts of this category are subdivided into conjunctions of ‘additive’, ‘adversative’ and ‘variation’. The data reveals superseding effect of conjunctions of additive category especially of the conjunction of ‘and’ (4004). The conjunctions of ‘also’ (256) and ‘further’ (37). ‘In addition’ (08), ‘furthermore (06) and ‘additionally’ (03) are the least selected conjunctions and that too by the writers of The Tribune Express. The corpus of DAWN doesn’t share any instance of their use.

Figure 4a: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts in the subcategories of extension

Figure 4b: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts except ‘and’ in the subcategories of extension

In the sub-category of ‘adversative’, the conjunction of ‘but’ with an overall frequency of 517 dominates other conjunctions of this category in the data of both newspapers. The conjunctions of ‘however’ (85), ‘yet’ (73), ‘instead’ (29) and ‘on the other hand’ (20) shows greater tendency use in comparison to ‘on the contrary’ (04) and ‘conversely’

(02). It is revealed that ‘but’ (261) is more favoured by the writers of DAWN whereas Tribune writers have used it less frequently (256).

The least frequently used subtype of extension is ‘variation’ as shown by the data of this corpus based study. All the conjunctions provided by the Halliday and Hasan’s model i.e. ‘instead’ (29), ‘on the contrary’ (04), ‘apart from that’ (0), ‘except for that’ (0), ‘except that’ (03) and ‘alternatively’ (02) have a total frequency of 38. The conjunctive adjunct ‘except that’ is used only by writers of The Express Tribune.

The conjunctive phases ‘apart from that’ and ‘except for that’ are not used by the writers of both Pakistani newspapers. Chart without the conjunction of ‘AND’ to show the frequencies of other conjunction that were veiled in the previous chart of extension category.

Overall, for the purposeful extension in the meaning of the text ‘and’ (4004), ‘but’ (517) and ‘also’ (256) are predominantly used cohesive devices in the corpus of the sample Pakistani newspapers. Corpus data reveals that ‘Additive’ conjunctions with a predominant number of 4382 are the most frequently used conjunctions not only in the extension category but also among all the categories shared by the Halliday and Hasan’s model of conjunctions.

4.5. Enhancement

Halliday and Hasan has classified the category of enhancement in the sub-categories of Spatio-Temporal, Manner, Causal-conditional and Respective. The Spatio-Temporal conjunctions are further classified into simple, complex and simple-internal types of conjunctive adjuncts.

4.6. Spatio-Temporal

The category is subdivided further into the following contexts:

4.7. Simple

With respect to the conjunctions of simple contexts, the study exhibits that the conjunctive adjuncts ‘then’ (94), ‘before’ (77) and ‘next’ (57) show the greater tendency of use whereas ‘finally’ (18), ‘at the same time’ (10) ‘after that’ (02) and ‘previously’ (02) are among the least used by the columnists. Further, some other least used conjunctions like ‘just then’ (01), ‘instantly’ (01), ‘in/at/to the end’ (08) are only used in the corpus of Tribune newspaper. The conjunction of ‘hitherto’ appears at only one instance and that too in the corpus of DAWN. The conjunctive phrase ‘before that’ and ‘first.....then’ are not at all used by the writers.

Figure 5: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts of subcategory simple

4.8. Complex

The study exhibits that among the conjunctions of complex contexts in the Spatio-Temporal references, the conjunctive adjuncts ‘later’ (38), ‘soon’ (23), ‘meanwhile’ (17) and ‘till’ (11) have some notable frequency of use in comparison to other conjunctions of complex textual contexts. The conjunctions of immediate and punctiliar contexts are not used in this corpus of sample of newspapers. In interruptive concerns, only the adjunct of ‘soon’ is used whereas the conjunctive phrase ‘after a while’ is not at all used in the corps of both newspapers however, data presents one instance of use of ‘in a while’ in the Tribune data. Among the conjunctions of repetitive concerns like ‘next time’, ‘on another occasion’, ‘occasionally’ and ‘next day’, only the conjunction of ‘occasionally’ (04) is used. Among adjuncts of specific Spatio-Temporal nature, only ‘later’ (38) is used while the use of ‘an hour later’ and ‘next morning’ is not revealed by the study. In the durative context, the conjunctive adjunct ‘meanwhile’ (17) is used while ‘all that time’ is not used by the writers. Only the conjunction of ‘till’ (11) is used to show terminal concerns in the text whereas the conjunction of ‘up to that point’ is not at all chosen in this context.

Figure 6: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts of subcategory complex

Figure 7: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts of subcategory simple-internal

4.9. Simple internal

In the simple internal contexts as shown in Figure 6, a list of conjunctions is mentioned by the model to bring in cohesion in the text. The study reveals that ‘now’ (127), ‘next’ (57) and ‘here’ (45) are more preferred by the Pakistani newspaper columnists whereas, ‘secondly’ (05), ‘finally’ (04), lastly (01) and hitherto (01) are the least opted choices for developing cohesion in the text. Further, ‘my next point is, first...next, at this point, up to now and last of all are not even once selected in the whole corpus. Finally (04) is only used in DAWN data and lastly (01) is presented by Tribune only.

4.10. Manner

The category is subdivided further into the contexts of comparison and means:

Figure 8: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts of subcategory of comparison

4.11. Comparative

‘Similarly’ (13) is frequent in use in comparison with ‘likewise’ (03) for comparative concerns by the writers of sample Pakistani newspapers. It is, however, exhibited that longer conjunctive phrases like ‘in the same way’, ‘in a different way’ and ‘in the same manner’ are not chosen by the writers of both newspapers.

4.12. Causal-conditional

The category is further divided into the contexts of causal and conditional:

Figure 9: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts of causal references

4.13. Causal

Causal-conditional is a sub-category for materializing textual functions of enhancement. For causal references, conjunctions can be of general as well as specific nature. In general references ‘for’ (1103) is the most frequently used conjunction followed by ‘so’ (168), ‘then’ (94), ‘because of’ (39) and ‘therefore’ (37). The conjunctions like ‘hence’ (13) and ‘consequently’ (07) are least used by the writers. According to data, conjunctions for specific causal concerns are less used by the writers than the general causal concerns. However, a few instances are shown by the corpus like ‘as a result’ (15), ‘for this/that reason’ (03), ‘on account of’ (02) and ‘for this/ that purpose’ (01). No instance of use of ‘in consequence’ and ‘with this/that in mind/view is found in the data.

Figure 10: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts of conditional references

4.14. Conditional

Among conjunctions of conditional references ‘then’ (98), ‘however’ (85) ‘yet’ (73), ‘still’ (58), and ‘though’ (35) show enhanced inclination of the writers for their selection to develop conditional contexts in the newspaper text. ‘If not’ (14), ‘otherwise’ (08), ‘nevertheless’ (07), ‘in this/that case’ (06), ‘despite this/that’ (04) and ‘nonetheless’ (02) are least used

whereas conjunctions like ‘in this/that event’, ‘under the circumstances’, ‘even so’, and ‘all the same’ are not at all chosen by them for the fulfillment of this function.

4.15. Respective

The conjunctions like ‘there’ (283), ‘here’ (45) and ‘elsewhere’ (06) show some frequency of use in respective conjunctive contexts. Here again the data represents that longer phrases like ‘as to that’, ‘in this/that respect’, ‘as far as that is / it is concerned’ and ‘in other respects’ are not at all favoured by the Pakistani columnists. Further, the study reveals that elsewhere is more chosen by the DAWN writers.

Figure 11: Frequency distribution of cohesive adjuncts of conditional references

5. Discussion

The results of the study prove the results of Qasim et al. (2020) with the highest frequency of use of additive conjunctions. Among additive conjunctions, the conjunction of “and” is used in superseding numbers by the writers. The conjunctions of causative category follow the trend of additive category with “for” as the dominant conjunction. Next, the trend is followed by the adversative conjunction “but”. The conjunctions of elaboration category are the least used among the three main categories of conjunctions; however, conjunctions of comparative and variation sub-categories of enhancement and extension types of conjunctions are least used by the writers/columnists of both English newspapers.

The tendency of usage is same among the most frequently used conjunctions; however, slight variations are observed in the choice of least used conjunctions like ‘hitherto’, ‘now’, ‘meanwhile’, ‘likewise’, etc. between the writers of DAWN and The Express Tribune. For example, the conjunctive adjunct ‘hitherto’ is once used in the whole corpus of both newspapers and that too by in the DAWN newspaper data.

Another observation is that writers of DAWN use relatively lesser number of conjunctions in comparison to opinion columnists of Tribune. In DAWN articles, writers have a tendency towards frequently employing commonly used conjunctive adjuncts. However, the writers of The Express Tribune use a greater variety of conjunctive adjuncts to express cohesive linkages in the text.

Pakistani English is an institutionalized variety (Kachru & Nelson, 2006) that has its distinct features (Mahboob, 2009; Rahman, 2020). Writers of Pakistani newspapers have their inclinations or favoured choices. Many of the conjunctive adjuncts mentioned in the Halliday and Hasan’s system of conjunction are most favoured to be chosen for the cohesive textual functions whereas some other adjuncts are totally discarded or not used by the writers of both newspapers. Here, it was revealed that the longer conjunctive phrases have greater chances for staying out of the text. However, one word conjunctions or conjunctive phrases of shorter length have greater probability of being chosen. The study exhibited that Pakistani writers of English newspapers use some one word substitutions for conjunctive phrases; for example, ‘particularly’ is more favoured choice than the entry word ‘in particular’ mentioned in the model. Similar is the case with the adjuncts of ‘precisely’ replacing ‘to be precise’, ‘rather’ in place of ‘or rather’ and ‘especially’ as a substitute of ‘more especially’, etc. The feature can be a characteristic of Pakistani English vocabulary.

5.1. Limitation

Depending upon their context of use, some of the conjunctive adjuncts/devices also works as *modal* or *circumstantial adjuncts*; for example, ‘actually’, ‘still’ and ‘yet’ are the few lexical items that can be categorized as *modal* as well as *conjunctive cohesive adjuncts*. In order to identify conjunctive adjuncts *textual metafunction* of conjunctive adjuncts is kept in consideration. (*Literary Stylistics Lecture Notes No. 18c, by Ismail Talib: Conjunctive Cohesion, n.d*)

6. Conclusion

The numerical results of this study reveals the category of extension as most frequently used category across the articles of both newspapers. The most influential and predominant conjunctions are of additive category. Causative sub-category of enhancement and adversative sub-category of extension follow the additive category in this trend of higher frequencies

of use. Elaboration is the least used category among the three main categories. Variation and comparative are the least used sub-categories of conjunctions. The study also concludes that writers' preferences for selection of conjunctions can be an insight towards distinctive features of Pakistani English.

6.1. Future Research Direction

The study can be extended in terms of a more extensive study utilizing corpus of majority of Pakistani English newspapers and drawing its comparison with the corpus of English newspapers writings of native countries.

References

- Ahmad, M., Mahmood, M. A., & Siddique, A. R. (2019). Organisational skills in academic writing: A study on coherence and cohesion in Pakistani research abstracts. *Languages*, 4(4), 92.
- Ahmad, M., Mahmood, M. A., Mahmood, M. I., & Siddique, A. R. (2019). Use of modal verbs as stance markers in Pakistani English newspaper editorials. *Online Journal of Communication and Media Technologies*, 9(1), e201903.
- Alasmri, I., & Kruger, H. (2018). Conjunctive markers in translation from English to Arabic: A corpus-based study. *Perspectives*, 26(5), 767-788.
- AlAttar, F. H., & Abu-Ayyash, E. A. (2022). An investigation of the use of conjunctive cohesive devices in Emirati students' argumentative essays.
- Bahaziq, A. (2016). Cohesive Devices in Written Discourse: A Discourse Analysis of a Student's Essay Writing. *English Language Teaching*, 9(7), 112-119.
- Batool, A. (2020). *A Corpus-Based Study Of Conjunctive Cohesion In Pakistani Research Articles*. Unpublished thesis. Government College University Faisalabad.
- Baumgardner, R. J. (1988). The Pakistanization of English. *Higher Education News*, 8(12), 2-7.
- Baumgardner, R. J. (Ed.). (1993). *The English Language in Pakistan*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Castro, C. D. (2004). Cohesion and the social construction of meaning in the essays of Filipino college students writing in L2 English. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 5(2), 215-225.
- Chen, C. W. Y. (2006). The use of conjunctive adverbials in the academic papers of advanced Taiwanese EFL learners. *International journal of corpus linguistics*, 11(1), 113-130.
- Chen, J. (2017). A Corpus-Based Study of Chinese EFL Learners' Employment of "Although". *English Language Teaching*, 10(8), 51-62.
- Crystal, D. (2003). *English as a global language*. Cambridge university press.
- Ganie, R., Sinar, T. S., & Yusuf, M. (2021). Conjunctive Markers in Students' Theses; Systemic Functional Perspective.
- Halliday, M. A. K. & Matthiessen, C.M.(2014). *An introduction to Functional Grammar*. 3rd eds. London: Routledge.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Hasan, R. (1976). *Cohesion in English*. London: Longman.
- Hamed, M. (2014). Conjunctions in Argumentative Writing of Libyan Tertiary Students. *English Language Teaching*, 7(3), 108-120.
- Hutton, L., & Curzan, A. (2019). The Grammatical Status of However. *Journal of English Linguistics*, 47(1), 29-54.
- Haratyan, F. (2011, October). Halliday's SFL and social meaning. In *2nd International Conference on Humanities, Historical and Social Sciences* (Vol. 17, No. 1, pp. 260-264).
- Jamalzadeh, M. (2017). A Corpus-based Study of Cohesive Conjunctions in Medical Research Articles Written by Iranian and Non-Iranian Authors. *Journal of Teaching English for Specific and Academic Purposes*, 669-686.
- Jambak, V. T., & Gurning, B. (2014). Cohesive devices used in the headline news of the Jakarta post. *Linguistica*, 3(1), 146298.
- Kachru, B. B. (Ed.). (1992). *The other tongue: English across cultures*. University of Illinois press.
- Kachru, Y., & Nelson, C. L. (2006). *World Englishes in Asian contexts*. Hong Kong: Hong Kong University Press ; London.
- Ketabi, S., & Jamalvand, A. A. (2012). A corpus-based study of conjunction devices in English international law texts and its Farsi translation. *International Journal of Linguistics*, 4(4), 362.
- Khan & Choudhary. (2017). A corpus-based study of Conjunction in Mohsin Hamid's Novels. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*.
- Khan, H. I. (2012). The evolution of Pakistani English (PakE) as a legitimate variety of English. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*, 1(5), 90-99.
- Kirkpatrick, A. (2007). *World Englishes: Implications for international communication and English language teaching*. Cambridge Univ Press.
- Literary Stylistics Lecture Notes no. 18c, by Ismail Talib: Conjunctive Cohesion*. (n.d.). Courses.nus.edu.sg. Retrieved December 31, 2022, from <https://courses.nus.edu.sg/course/ellibst/lsl18c.html#:~:text=From%20a%20non%2Dtechnical%20perspective>
- Liu, M., & Braine, G. (2005). Cohesive features in argumentative writing produced by Chinese undergraduates. *System*, 33(4), 623-636.
- Mahboob, A., Ahmar, (2004). *Pakistani English: phonology*. In N. H., Kortmann, B., & Traugott, E. (eds.). *A Handbook of Varieties of English*.

- Mahboob, A. (2009). English as an Islamic language: a case study of Pakistani English. *World Englishes*, 28(2), 175-189.
- Martínez, A. C. L. (2015). Use of conjunctions in the compositions of secondary education students. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 212, 42-46.
- Michel, M. C. (2013). The use of conjunctions in cognitively simple versus complex oral L2 tasks. *The Modern Language Journal*, 97(1), 178-195.
- Mohammed, A. S. (2015). Conjunctions as cohesive devices in the writings of English as second language learners. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 208, 74-81.
- Mahmood, M. A. (2009). A corpus based analysis of Pakistani English. *Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan*.
- Mushtaq, H., Bhatti, A.M. & Yasmin, T. (2021). A Corpus Based Vocabulary Analysis of Intermediate Book 1 used in the College of Punjab. *Competitive Linguistic Research Journal*, 2(1), 31-57.
- Namazandost, E., Nasri, M., & Keshmirshakan, M. H. (2019). Cohesive conjunctions in applied linguistics research articles among Iranian and non-Iranian researchers: A comparative corpus-based study. *Journal of English Language Studies*, 4(2), 101-119.
- Narita, M., Sato, C., & Sugiura, M. (2004, May). Connector Usage in the English Essay Writing of Japanese EFL Learners. In *LREC* (Vol. 27, pp. 1171-1174).
- Qasim, H. M., Batool, A., & Nawaz, M. S. (2020). A corpus-based study of conjunctive cohesion in Pakistani research articles. *International Journal of Linguistics and Culture*, 1(2), 111-132.
- Qasim, H. M., HM, S. M., & Sibtain, M. (2021). Locus of Conjunctions in Academic Writing: A Corpus-Driven Approach to Developing Writing among EFL Learners. *Pakistan Languages and Humanities Review*, 5(2), 432-443.
- Rahman, T. (1991). *Pakistani English: some phonological and phonetic features*. Pergamon.
- Rahman, T. (2020). Pakistani English. *The handbook of Asian englishes*, 279-296.
- Schneider, E. W. (2003). The dynamics of New Englishes: From identity construction to dialect birth. *Language*, 79(2), 233-281.
- Shahnaz, A., & Imtiaz, A. (2014). How a text binds together: discourse analysis of a newspaper article. *International Journal of English and Education*, 3(1), 238-249.
- Talaat, M. (2002). The sociolinguistics of English in Pakistan: Form and functions. *Unpublished Ph. D. thesis. Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan*.
- Trebits, A. (2009). Conjunctive cohesion in English language EU documents—A corpus-based analysis and its implications. *English for Specific Purposes*, 28(3), 199-210.
- Yang, W., & Sun, Y. (2012). The use of cohesive devices in argumentative writing by Chinese EFL learners at different proficiency levels. *Linguistics and education*, 23(1), 31-48.
- Zhang, A. (2010). Use of cohesive ties in relation to the quality of compositions by Chinese college students.